

Some Constituents of *Cæsalpinia Bonducella* Nut (Flem).

Part I. Bonducella Nut Oil.

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Cæsalpinia bonducella is a climbing shrub common all over Bengal, Bombay, Travancore and the Coromondal coast. It is known in Hindi as the Sagargota plant. The dry nut has an iron grey colour with a very hard and flexible rind which causes it to bounce like a ping-pong ball when it impinges on a hard surface. It is well-known in Indian homes especially among children. It has been recognised for a long time that the kernels of these nuts have anti-periodic and febrifuge properties. It is known abroad as the fever nut, and is thus administered in cases of intermittent fevers and cholera. The usual dose is from 5 to 30 grains. (Watt. "Dictionary of Economic Products of India," Vol. II, p. 4).

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to detect those substances in the nut which give it these characteristic properties. Before proceeding to the glucosides, we considered it advisable to examine the constituents of its oil, obtained from the petrol extracts of the dried and crushed kernels.

The nuts average 1.8 to 2 gm. in weight. The proportion of rind to kernel is 58.1 to 41.9. The percentage of oil yield, when extracted with petrol ether (60°—80°), on dried kernels was 20. The oil has a peculiar odour and a pale yellow colour. Lewkowitch ("Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats and Waxes," 4th Ed., Vol. II, p. 192) mentions this as a semi-drying oil with a dark colour and peculiar odour. The petrol extracted kernels were tested for elements and gave positive tests for sulphur and nitrogen.

The nuts were pressed in a local *Ghana* and the oil obtained was clear and pale yellow in colour; the quantity pressed being small, the percentage yield of oil, by this method, could not be calculated on account of wastage during the pressing operations.

The petrol ether extracted kernels were further extracted with absolute alcohol. On cooling the extract, a thick white precipitate

was obtained which was soluble in water (with frothing) and was identified as saponin. The alcohol was removed and the residue reduced Fehling's solution on hydrolysis with acid and was obviously a glucoside. This is the bitter principle which contains almost all the sulphur content of the *Bonducella* nut.

On treating the alcohol extracted kernel with distilled water, a further quantity of saponin was obtained. The baryta compound was precipitated, washed and decomposed with carbon dioxide, when saponin was obtained by concentrating the filtrate.

In another experiment the kernel, after the first petrol ether extraction, was further extracted with 2 % hydrochloric acid. This latter extract, on neutralisation with sodium carbonate solution, yielded a fluffy precipitate which was washed and preserved for further examination. It gave a feeble nitrogen test, but sulphur could not be detected. The fluffy precipitate was soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid and gave precipitates with picric acid and Froehde's reagent. The two dried precipitates, as well as the original substance, did not melt even at 295° but showed a slight charring only. This substance in dilute sulphuric acid solution decolorised potassium permanganate solution.

The work on the *Bonducella* oil was conducted on the usual lines. The constants of the oil and the fatty acids were determined. The saturated and unsaturated acids were separated by Twitchell's (*J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806) lead-salt-alcohol method from the mixed fatty acids liberated from the ether-extracted dry soap. The composition of the unsaturated acids was determined from the iodine value and the bromination products, and that of the saturated acids by fractional crystallisation and the examination of the methyl esters of the completely hardened acids.

The hydrogenation of the oil was carried out with nickel-pumice catalyst, and the relation between the refractive index and iodine value of the various samples, taken out at intervals during the process of hydrogenation, was determined.

Tanaka's modified castor-seed-lipase-hydrolysis method showed that while the lipase could effect the hydrolysis of the common oils like sesame, ground-nut, etc., it had no effect on *Bonducella* oil under the conditions of the experiment. This is similar to the action of mustard oil in its inhibiting effect on lipase. This matter is being investigated further.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Constants of Bonducella Oil (Flem).

Refractive index	...	1.4750 at 25°.
Saponification value	...	199.5—200.5.
Iodine value (Winkler)	...	127.
Specific gravity	...	0.9215 at 28°/15°C.
Acetyl value	...	Nil.
Polensky value	...	Nil.
Hehner number	...	93.
Unsaponifiable matter	...	1.5%

Lewkowitsch (*loc. cit.*) gives the iodine value for oil (*Cæsalpinia Bonducella*, Roxb.) as 89.9, and Bhaduri (*Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 28, 53) gives the following figures:—S. V. 292.8, I. V. 96.1, D_{27}° 0.9132.

The fatty acids were liberated by decomposing the ether-extracted dry soap with dilute hydrochloric acid. The fatty acids, free from hydrochloric acid, were heated up to 120° in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide in order to remove the last traces of water.

Constants of the fatty acids.

Mean molecular weight	...	287.5
Iodine value	...	136
Titre value	...	19.2°
Saponification value	...	126.5

Hydrogenation of the oil.

The hydrogenation was carried out with the nickel-pumice catalyst prepared by reducing the dried nickel carbonate, precipitated on pumice, in a current of hydrogen at 300°. A temperature of 180° was maintained during the hydrogenation and it was noticed in a number of batches that the catalyst did not function at the first attempt. However, when the same sample of the oil treated as above was filtered and charged with fresh catalyst, the hydrogenation proceeded normally. It was also noticed that the stirring was accompanied by much frothing. This does not occur with other common oils like ground-nut, sesame, linseed, etc. These two peculiarities were also particularly noticed in the case of mustard oils when similarly hydrogenated.

Several samples of the oil were removed during the progress of hydrogenation. Their iodine values and refractive indices were determined and the curve showing the relation between them is shown in Fig. I. One point with 59 I.V. falls outside the curve.

FIG. I.

The relation between the refractive indices and iodine values.

The saturated acids.—The saturated acids from the mixed fatty acids were estimated by Twitchell's lead-salt-alcohol method. The percentage of saturated acids was 16 on the total mixed acids with mean molecular weight 269.5, and iodine value practically *nil*. The titre of the saturated acids was 56°.

The unsaturated acids.—The unsaturated acids were obtained by decomposing the lead salts of the liquid acids with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracting them with ether. They formed 84 % of the mixed acids. Their mean molecular weight was 283 and iodine value 157.6.

The unsaturated acids were examined by their bromine additive compounds as recommended by Jamieson and Baughman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 2398.)

About 5 gm. of the acids were weighed out and dissolved in 100 c.c. dry ether with 2 c.c. glacial acetic acid, cooled in ice and brominated with dry bromine. On cooling the mixture for two hours in ice, no precipitate of hexa-bromide separated out showing the absence of linolinic acid. The ethereal solution was then washed free from bromine with sodium thiosulphate solution, and afterwards freed from the thiosulphate. It was finally dried on anhydrous sodium sulphate, and the total bromides were obtained on evaporation of ether. These were further dried in vacuum and weighed.

In the absence of the hexabromide, which indicates the absence of linolinic acid, the proportion of linoleic to oleic acid works out from the iodine value as 73.92% to 26.08%, which is in agreement with the results obtained from the bromination products shown under the columns A and B in Table I.

TABLE I.

	A	B
Quantity brominated.	... 5.086 gm.	6.250 gm.
Hexabromide.	... Nil.	Nil.
Yield of di- and tetra-bromides.	... 10.201 gm.	12.415 gm.
Calculated yield from above percentage of oleic to linoleic acid.	... 10.150 gm.	12.450 gm.
M.p. of tetrabromide (cryst. from petrol).	... 113°	118°

The composition of the saturated acids.

6.56 Gm. of the saturated acids were subjected to crystallisation from 90% alcohol and separated into two fractions:

(1) 1st crop (α)—3.23 gm.; m.p. 57°, M. W. 271.

(2) Recovered from filtrate—3.33 gm.; m.p. 57°, M.W. 263.

According to the mixture tables (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, Vol. 6. Part 6, pp. 126—127, Table II; Lewkowitsch "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats and Waxes", 1921, Vol. I, p. 118), (1) and (2) give definite points on the palmitic-stearic mixture curve. The composition of the original saturated acids works out at 63% palmitic and 37% stearic, thus giving in the original oil 10.08% of palmitic and 5.92% of stearic acids.

Crop (a) was further crystallised first from acetone and afterwards from a very small quantity of 90% alcohol. Crop (b) was thus obtained, having 63° m.p. and 277 M.W. This crop (b) also gives a point on the palmitic-stearic curve with 73% stearic and 27% palmitic acids.

Acid (b) was further crystallised and after four crystallisations a very small quantity of glistening plates was left when the melting point had risen to 69°. A mixed melting point was taken with pure crystallised stearic acid melting at 69°, M.W. 284 and no lowering of melting point was noticed. This proved that the higher acid present in the mixture was stearic acid.

The composition of the saturated acids was also determined by hydrogenating the original oil, liberating the acids and then examining the methyl esters by fractional distillation under a pressure of 25 mm.

TABLE II.

Refractionation of methyl esters of hardened acids from Bonducella oil.

I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
Fraction.	Boiling range.	Weight in gms.	Titre.	Mean M.W.	M.W. of acids calc. from ester value.	M.p. (acids).	Palmitic p.c. from IV, VI & VIII.	Stearic p.c. from IV, VI & VII.
1.	232°	8.6	28.5°	285.1	271.1	60°	40	60
2.	232° 234°	9.97	31.5°	291.2	277.2	65°	22	78
3.	234°	15.05	33.2°	294.5	280.5	66°	15	85
4.	235° 237°	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	237°	29.50	34.5°	294.6	280.6	67°	10	90
5.	237°	35.00	35.2°	298.2	284.2	67°	—	100
Residue.	241° & above	9.12	—	—	—	—	—	92

The values given in columns IV, VI and VII of Table II are in good agreement with the required percentages shown in columns VIII and IX with the exception of fraction 5 where the titre of the ester and the melting point of acids are a degree or so lower than in the case of pure stearic acid. The iodine value of this fraction was found to be 4. This explains its lower melting point. On one crystallisation from alcohol pure stearic acid was obtained. The percentage of the liquid acids from this iodine value being negligible, fraction 5 is treated in the calculation as pure stearic acid. In the

residue the iodine value was found to be 8. The ester was then decomposed, the acids liberated and crystallised from 90% alcohol. In two crystallisations, a clean acid, having m.p. 69° and M. W. 288.6 was obtained showing that the higher acid contained in the residue was stearic acid only. After allowing for the presence of the liquid acids from the iodine value, the whole of the residue was taken to be stearic acid.

From the percentages of the acids the quantities of palmitic and stearic acids were calculated on the weights of the different fractions as given in the following table.

TABLE III.

Fraction.	Wt. of palmitic acid.	Weight of stearic acid.
1	3.44 gm.	5.16 gm.
2	2.19 gm.	7.78 gm.
3	2.25 gm.	12.80 gm.
4	2.95 gm.	26.55 gm.
5	—	35.00 gm.
Residue.	—	8.32 gms.
	10.83 gm.	95.61 gm.

Total = 106.44 gms.

Thus the composition of the hardened acids is 10.16 % palmitic acid and 89.84 % stearic acid. This is in fair agreement with the previous results obtained by direct examination of the saturated acids.

Table IV gives the composition of (a) the acids from the hardened oil, (b) the mixed acids from the original oil and (c) the oil itself.

TABLE IV.

	(a) P.c. in hardened acids.	(b) P.c. in mixed acids.	(c) P.c. of the corresponding glycerides in the oil.
Palmitic acid.	10.16	10.16	10.00
Stearic acid.	89.84	5.84	5.79
Oleic acid.	—	21.91	21.60
Linoleic acid.	—	62.09	61.40
Unsaponifiable matter.	—	—	1.5.

The unsaponifiable matter.

On the extraction of the dry soap with ether in the Soxhlet extractor, a deep yellow coloured residue was obtained which, on being allowed to stand, yielded a yellow needle-shaped crystalline substance with a peculiar odour. This odour was noticed while dealing with the unsaponifiable matter from the Indian soap nut oil. The residue was completely soluble in absolute alcohol and, on crystallisation from 98% alcohol, yielded a crystalline sterol melting at 135°. Viewed under a microscope the crystals showed the characteristic shapes of sitosterol crystals. One of the constituents in the unsaponifiable matter thus appears to be sitosterol.

Summary.

(1) *C. Bonducella* nut kernels yield 20 per cent. of the fixed oil on extraction with petrol ether. The oil has a pale yellow colour and a characteristic odour.

(2) The glucoside separated from the oil-extracted kernel with alcohol contains most of the sulphur of the *Bonducella* nut.

(3) Attempts to separate the alkaloid did not meet with success.

(4) *Bonducella* oil has a poisoning effect on the nickel catalyst similar to mustard oils. The oil is hardened, however, on using a fresh catalyst.

(5) The iodine value—refractive index curve shows a bending near 90 (iodine values). One point with 59 I.V. falls outside the curve.

(6) The acids present are in the form of glycerides of oleic, linoleic, palmitic and stearic acids. The main peculiarity noticed is the large proportion of linoleic to oleic and similarly of palmitic to stearic acid. This is not generally the case with the common oils. Their composition is shown in Table IV.

(7) *Bonducella* oil has an inhibiting action on castor seed lipase.